

Neuron as an Electric PAU

Dante Roberto Salatino★ - Alfredo Ernesto Puglesi★★

About the authors

★Dante Roberto Salatino is a researcher of the Institute of Philosophy and of the Institute of Linguistics - Lecturer in the General Psychology Department – Lecturer in the Philosophical Aspects of Physical-Mathematical Science Department - Faculty of Philosophy and Letters - Teacher and Researcher in Artificial Intelligence in the Mechatronics Career - Faculty of Engineering - National University of Cuyo, Mendoza, Argentina - Email for correspondence: dantesalatino@gmail.com

★★Alfredo Ernesto Puglesi is Consultant Professor in the specialties of "Instrumentation and Automatic Control" and "Applied Computing" in the careers of Petroleum Engineering, Industrial Engineering and Mechatronics of the National University of Cuyo, Mendoza, Argentina. Email for correspondence: apuglesi@yahoo.com.ar

ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to show that it is possible to describe, in approximate form, the operation of a neuron if it is defined from the electrical point of view. To create the neurons that make up artificial neural networks were used as a resource the *deus ex machina*. That is, an external element was sought to solve the problem, ignoring its internal logic. Llinás (1988) showed that a neuron in mammals is not only that 'ideal cell' that helped to unravel all the researchers before him, but also represents a dynamic element that has a wide range of electrophysiological properties that allow it to handle different ionic conductances, either dependent on a certain voltage level, or on some molecule that activates them. Among the electrophysiological properties of the CNS neurons, Llinás highlights its spontaneous activity, which is closely linked to the voltage-activated ionic conductions, in particular, the one is known as the low threshold of Ca^{++} initially identified in the cells of the inferior olive (IO). Thus, neurons become true unicellular oscillators or resonators. The self-rhythmicity that enables Ca^{++} and other ions make a nerve cell can respond to certain frequencies. According to a theory of neuropsychic functioning (Salatino, 2013) is that they are described and substantiated from the electrical point of view, each of the parts that make up a neuron. That is: 1) Dendrites as an RC circuit that acts as a receiver (or tuner); 2) Soma as an RL circuit that by a phenomenon of self-induction justifies the generation of the "action potential"; 3) Dendrite-soma complex as an RLC circuit that acts as a resonator, generating certain frequencies; and 4) Axon-synapse complex as an RM (resistor-memristor) circuit that allows to "remember" a particular frequency. This allows us to see the neuron as an integrator of the passive electrical elements (that dissipate or store energy) of two terminals, which, according to the classical circuit theory, are three: the capacitor, the resistor, and the inductor. A fourth basic element is included: the memristor, whose operation can only be detected at the nanoscale. The four fundamental variables that define the aforementioned elements are: a) electrical voltage, b) electric current, c) electric charge and d) magnetic flux. With them, different PAUs were created that allowed, through the Transcursive Logic, to simulate the electrical functioning of a neuron. This operation was corroborated by industrial simulators of electrical circuits.

Keyword: neurophysiology, electrical theory, psychic functioning, Transcursive Logic.

CITATION:

Salatino, D. R.; Puglesi, A. E. (2018). "Neuron as an electric PAU" *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 4, No. 4: pp. 59-76. (Oct. – Dec. 2018); ISSN: 2415-0371.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2545020

1.0 INTRODUCTION

To create the neurons that make up artificial neural networks were used as a resource the *deus ex machina*. That is, an external element was sought to solve the problem, ignoring its internal logic.

It is possible to describe, in approximate form, the operation of a neuron if it is defined from the electrical point of view.

Since the end of the eighteenth century, the existence of animal current is known, through the experiments of Galvani (1797). In the mid-nineteenth century, Matteucci (1844) describes the “current of injury or muscular.” Helmholtz (1854) calculated the velocity of propagation of the excitatory signal in a neuro-muscular preparation. At the same time, Du Bois-Reymond (1849), discovered the “action potential” of a nerve, through its electrical stimulation, and it was Bernstein (1868) who determined its velocity of propagation and proposed that the living cell was surrounded by a cellular membrane slightly permeable to ions and that the interior was filled with an electrolyte where the ions moved freely.

Began the twentieth century, many were the contributions that pin down the electrical characteristics of both the nerve and the cell membrane. Walther Nernst (1907) proposed that both the nerve cell membrane and the muscle membrane were polarized due to their selective permeability to potassium. Thus, he managed to explain the 'resting potential' as a consequence of a selective permeability between cations and anions.

The intracellular measurements made by Hodgkin and Huxley (1952) led to determine the differential equations that explained the mechanism of ionic conductances producing the action potential and the behavior of the nerve as an electric conductor. For these results, they were deserving of the Nobel Prize in Medicine in 1963.

Llinás (1988) showed that a neuron in mammals is not only that 'ideal cell' that helped to unravel all the previous researchers, but also represents a dynamic element that has a wide range of electrophysiological properties that allow it to handle different ionic conductances, either dependent on a certain voltage level, or on some molecule that activates them.

Among the electrophysiological properties of the CNS neurons, Llinás highlights its spontaneous activity, which is closely linked to the voltage-activated ionic conductions, in particular, the one is known as the low threshold of Ca^{++} initially identified in the cells of the inferior olive (IO).

The aforementioned spontaneous activity has a particularity and is that it is inactivated during the resting potential and is reactivated during hyperpolarization of the membrane. The latter is a behavior that seems paradoxical, as it contradicts the 'neurobiological dogma' that states that the depolarization of the membrane from the resting potential increases excitability, while hyperpolarization decreases it. The dogmatic is an oversimplification, since, in the IO, a subthreshold depolarization can produce an action potential superimposed on depolarizations or hyperpolarizations. This phenomenon authorizes, that the CNS neurons to be considered as true unicellular oscillators or resonators.

The conductance of Ca^{++} as that of other ions is organized in such a way as to allow self-rhythmicity to a nerve cell. Also, as the dynamics of these conductances, in some cells, respond to a certain frequency (s), they can be considered as resonators. The best example of this is, again, the cells of the IO, which tend to respond to frequencies that are directly modulated by their intrinsic electrical properties.

2.0 A THEORY OF NEUROPSYCHICAL FUNCTIONING

Before describing a neuron from the electrical point of view, we will summarize a theory about psychic structure and function already elaborated (Salatino, 2013), under whose principles this neuron must operate. According to this theory everything that affects from the outside to our brain, as a stimulus, it does in the form of waves that have a certain range of frequencies. Therefore, the central nervous system (CNS) should be able to measure the frequency of the input wave and thus certify that something has been perceived. But, besides, depending on the frequency, it will tell us

to which part of the subjective reality (that of the subject that perceives - Salatino, 2009) belongs. That is, if what you just entered is about biological reality (stimuli from the body). With the psychic reality (stimuli that come from the immediate surroundings of the subject). Or with the sociocultural reality (stimuli originated in the relationship with others).

We must bear in mind that there is a specific sector of the brain, product of the phylogenetic evolution of the CNS, to respond to each of these instances (Salatino, 2012, p.82) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 shows synthetically the evolutionary integration that occurs in the human CNS. In the diagram, we can see the concurrence of three brains. The 'neuronal brain,' the oldest one, that sits in the basal ganglia, where the perceived element is a pure transformation or change through a 'signal.' The 'visceral brain' that lies in the limbic system, where 'objects' are perceived using a 'sign,' that is that indicates the relationship between two objects utilizing a change. Finally, the 'cortical brain,' the newest evolutionarily speaking, that from the cerebral cortex can detect 'subjects' with the help of a 'symbol,' that is, what records the relationship between a subject and an object thanks to a change or transformation.

Fig. 1. Filogenetic distribution of the SNC

References: inputs: signal, sign, symbol - outputs: PA_I : innate response; PA_E : modifiable response by experience - PA_A : learned response (Salatino, 2009).

The above scheme also tells us about the outputs (the response) projected by each of these 'brains.' Although, before producing an output, it must be elaborated. The elaboration of the answers, in the same way, is directly related to the frequency. The aforementioned theory tells us that there is a selector mechanism of each of the brains described, to 'take the data' that have entered and so proceed to elaborate a response and 'record it' before projecting it. That mechanism is seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Dopaminergic system

Dopamine is a neurotransmitter that is involved in all CNS responses. From the dopamine-producing areas, at the base of the brain, it is distributed to the nuclei and gray matter areas of the “different brains” to coordinate a specific response, register it and determine to what part of reality it is necessary to project it. These answers, as indicated in Figure 1, can be innate if they are directed to biology, modifiable with experience if the destination is the immediate environment, or directly learned if the objective of the projection is sociocultural ambit.

3.0 THE NEURON FROM THE ELECTRIC POINT OF VIEW

After reviewing the tasks that must be fulfilled by neurons and how they should be done, to emulate these processes succinctly, we present an “electrical model” of a generic neuron, and we do it from the Transcursive Logic (TL) (Salatino, 2017) (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Neuronal PAU

References: C: capacitance - R: resistance - L: Inductance; M: memristance - Δ : variation - S: subject - O: object; V: apparent transformation - ∇ : hidden transformation \otimes : XOR - \odot : XNOR.

The TL will constitute a practical guide of how to observe the dynamics of this system of transformations. Something similar to a “phase space” of 4 dimensions (4 variables). By locating the four fundamental variables that can dynamically define the system (3 apparent or known and one hidden or unknown), through a PAU (Universal Autonomous Pattern), a new panorama opens up in this portion of the reality that we are analyzing and that until the moment of the analysis was ignored. Like any guide, TL “simplifies” reality to emphasize certain aspects. For example, it is always possible to determine a 'trajectory' in this 'phase space' that is cyclical and borderline, both of the apparent and of what is not visible to the naked eye. In the case at hand, as we shall see, this is what happens with the inclusion of a memristor in a classic circuit. This ensures that the fundamental law is fulfilled so that the principles of the TL can be applied. That is that these four fundamental variables, this PAU form an algebraic structure called a group. This confirms that the 'simplified system' complies with the essential laws of symmetry that demonstrate the conservation and invariance of their relations before any possible variation driven by a transformation, as occurs in objective reality. In short, we make sure that there is a correspondence, fundamentally, between the reality analyzed and the proposed model.

With the previous scheme, it has been tried to represent, like an electrical circuit, the different components of a natural neuron. Thus, the surface level of the PAU (Ibidem, p.87) (green or apparent triangle) represents the point of entry of the electric impulse (dendrites). The deep level of the PAU (blue or hidden triangle) is equivalent to the neuronal body (soma). While the “theoretical connection” between the extremes of both levels, it takes the place of the cylinder axis or axon, which is where the 'action potential' is transmitted to the exit point: the synapse. The synapse represents the point of union between neurons and is where one neuron communicates with the dendrites of another neuron (s).

From the strictly electrical, the neuron can be seen as an integrator of the passive electrical elements (that dissipate or store energy) of two terminals. According to classical circuit theory, there are three basic elements: the capacitor, the resistor, and the inductor. In 1971, Professor L. Chua of the University of Berkeley predicted the existence of a fourth basic element that he called *memristor* (See Appendix). This element was initially defined as a mathematical entity since it usually functions 'hidden' because its unique properties only become apparent at the nanoscale (Vourkas & Sirakoulis, 2016, p. xii).

There are, in turn, four fundamental variables that define the elements mentioned above. These variables are: v (electrical voltage), i (electric current), q (electric charge), and ϕ (magnetic flux). Then, for the elements of two terminals, the relation between v and i defines the resistor as $dv = Rdi$. The relationship between q and v defines the capacitor as $dq = Cdv$. The relation between ϕ and i defines the inductor as $d\phi = Ldi$. Finally, Chua indicated that the relation between q and ϕ defined the memristor as $d\phi = Mdq$ (Radwan & Fouda, 2015, p 153).

As we can see in Figure 3, each variable has been assigned a binary code that responds to the attached table of assignments. This code allows glimpsing the origin of these variables. The voltage (v) arises from a variation of the magnetic flux ($\Delta\phi$), while the current (i) results from a variation of the electric charge (Δq). The charge (q) arises from a “composition” of v and i , while the magnetic flux (ϕ) does not depend on any of the two previous variables.

4.0 PROCESSING OF ELECTRICAL ACTIVITY

We will analyze how it is that a neuron, when receiving an external impulse (stimulus), generates an 'action potential' as an answer, although we will do it exclusively, from the electrical and not neurobiological point of view. Only as an analytical exercise, we will decompose this process in different stages according to the natural neuronal component involved, and we will match it with the respective structural or functional aspect of the PAU.

4.1 Dendrite – superficial level

Fig. 5. Soma electric circuit

The membrane of the postsynaptic neuron is the source of the synaptic current, which is generated with the arrival of stimuli (SVO) to the dendrites as we saw in the previous point, and which can produce an excitatory or inhibitory action. Figure 5 shows an excitatory synapse.

The release of excitatory neurotransmitters changes the ionic permeability of the postsynaptic membrane and produces a “postsynaptic potential” of long duration, but low voltage, although of an additive nature. Ultimately, for an “action potential” to occur, must reach the initial segment (SI in the figure) of the axon a depolarizing potential that exceeds the "threshold potential." The integration in the postsynaptic neuron, in this case, of signals that depolarize it is called “summation.” That is, the small postsynaptic potentials are accumulated by a “cycling” of the current between the input dendrite (represented by a resistance) and the SI, (represented by an inductor) until the 'threshold potential' is reached, the moment in which an 'action potential' is triggered (Randall et al., 1997, p 215).

We see in Figure 5 an electrical equivalent of the mechanism described above. The circuit that complies, approximately, with the previous mechanism is the RL (formed by a resistance (R) and an inductor (L)). The direction of circulation of the current in the circuit of the deep level is inverse (levorotatory) concerning that which had the surface level (dextrorotatory). This change of direction (clockwise → anticlockwise) is justified in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Parallel circuits

The above diagram represents the two levels of the PAU transformed into parallel circuits, where the surface level (S) represents the current source (I) that circulates clockwise through the capacitor (C) and the inductor (L). When the switch is opened, the current flows in the same direction as the surface resistance (R_s) as a consequence of what is stored in the capacitor (C). While it circulates in the opposite direction by the resistance (R_p) of the circuit that represents the deep level (P), as a product of what is stored in the inductor (L) (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Simulation with livewire© Copyright © New Wave Concepts Limited.

In RL circuits there is a phenomenon of self-inductance or inductance, which response to the property of the circuit to oppose variations in current intensity. This phenomenon is responsible for the delay of the current (i) concerning the voltage (v) applied and therefore that a certain time elapses until reaching its maximum level (equivalent to the time it takes the neuron to reach the threshold potential). The inductive property is manifested by the creation or induction of an opposite voltage (v_{ind}) whose value changes (increase \cong summation) moment by moment. The induced voltage (v_{ind}) is directly proportional to the rate of variation of the flow cuts. It will be maximum and will oppose with a value almost equal to the applied voltage when a zero level of external voltage and current is reached. The latter is equivalent, in the neuron, to have reached the “threshold potential” and triggered an 'action potential.' When the current is constant, there is no induced voltage (Siskind, 1972, p.216).

4.3 Dendrite-soma complex - PAU

When we close the circuit switch that represents the two levels of the PAU (Figure 8), it becomes a resonant circuit.

Fig. 8. Resonant circuit

References: I: current - C: capacitor - L: inductor - R_S : superficial resistance R_P : profound resistance
 - S: superficial level - P: profound level

The previous one is an RLC circuit (composed of resistors, inductor, and capacitor) in parallel, to which if an alternating current is applied it can enter into resonance when the total current (i) is in phase with the applied voltage (v). Under these conditions, the resulting reactance is zero. Two fundamental properties of the inductive reactance (X_L) and the capacitive reactance (X_C) make possible the resonance: a) they are opposite since they delay or advance the current by 90° , respectively and b) their opposite behavior against the frequency: directly proportional and inversely proportional, respectively (Ibidem, p.356).

In the case of the hypothetical neuron that we are considering, when we analyze it as a complete PAU, it behaves like an RLC circuit in series where an alternating current circulates (Figure 9).

Fig. 9. Neuron as a resonant circuit

References: C: capacitor - L: inductor - X_C : capacitive reactance. X_L : inductive reactance - q: charge
 - ϕ : magnetic flux - f: frequency \otimes : XOR - \ominus : XNOR

The resonance of a series circuit is independent of the resistance, that is, it is as if the resistance of the RLC circuit did not exist. It is only a function of the values of inductance and capacity, or what is the same, of the magnetic flux (ϕ) and the charge (q). For this reason, was elaborated the lower scheme in the previous figure. There, everything is planned to reach resonance, by varying the impedance (reactance + resistance) of the circuit. There are three ways to achieve the

above: 1) varying the frequency, 2) varying the inductance, or 3) varying the capacitance. It is assumed that, if the resistance is stable, the circuit will come into resonance if: a) for a particular frequency (f), the inductance (L) and the conductance (C) are fixed; b) for a particular value of L , f and C are fixed; or c) for a particular value of C if f and L are fixed. (Ibid, p.358). All these possibilities can be deduced from the table attached to the scheme, through the respective operations (\otimes and \odot) between the elements of this group that constitutes a PAU.

In the particular case, we are analyzing, a special type of PAU has been constituted, which is called “cyclical.” In this elementary arrangement, the dynamics of both levels (superficial/profound) is activated by a single operation (transformation) or using both simple operations at the same time. This way of projecting the transformations causes that, in some way, breaks with the 'golden rule' of the TL, which is: “The deep level of PAU cycles in the opposite direction to the superficial level.” Here, the profound level is 'dragged' by the superficial level with which a single cycle is formed (dextrorotatory or levorotatory, in an alternative way) that correctly defines the transformations present in the analyzed system. This alternation is nothing else than the phenomenon of resonance, which makes the system cycle at a certain frequency (frequency modulation), and with an adaptation of its phase (phase modulation). These characteristics would allow the neuron to specify (tune in) the system (biological, psychic or sociocultural) for which it has to prepare the response and do it correctly according to the experience acquired or learn a new way of responding.

4.4 Axon-synapse complex – plasticity – “bycyclic” PAU

The active way of conducting the 'action potential' generated in the initial segment (SI) along the axon, sometimes at a great distance, is through the voltage-activated ion channels. These channels (Na^+ and K^+) open and close with such a temporal precision that they can reverse, transiently, the 'membrane potential' (depolarization) that travels through the axon at a speed of 120 m / s. The longitudinal (passive) electrotonic propagation depends on the “cable” properties of the axon, that is, a succession of RC circuits in parallel (Randall et al., 1997, p.167).

When depolarization reaches the synapse, a complex series of modifications (not detailed) are produced that allow a modification of the excitability of the postsynaptic membrane, ensuring the conduction of the stimulus.

The chemical synapse as we have considered it forms a bipartite system in which the signal is transmitted between pre and postsynaptic cells. In the first decade of this century, an additional parameter was discovered that must be taken into account in the synaptic function. This component is astroglia, (tissue formed by astrocytes, the main and most abundant glial cell), participating in the control of the neuronal microenvironment (“tripartite synapse” hypothesis) (Pickel & Segal, 2014, page 379).

Another aspect that has recently become evident as a regulator of neuronal function and plasticity is the role played by the surrounding extracellular matrix, where arises the “quadripartite synapse hypothesis.” (Dityatev & Rusakov, 2011) emerging (Figure 10).

Fig. 10. PAU Tetrapartite synapse

The presynaptic neuron, according to the previous scheme, is the one that releases the neurotransmitter. Most information in the brain is processed through excitatory glutamatergic synapses. The presynaptic neuron is the one that releases the *glutamate* (neurotransmitter). Another of its activities has to do with the release of *neurotrypsin*, using which it controls the surrounding “Extracellular Matrix” (EMC). *Neurotrypsin* determines the production of *agrin* by the EMC that promotes, on the one hand, the development and maintenance of the neuromuscular junction. But on the other, one of the degradation products of agrin triggers the formation of “dendritic filopodia.”

It is accepted that Long-Term Potentiation (LTP), that is involved in neuronal plasticity, in the mechanism of memory and learning is expressed at the level of the postsynaptic neuron (as in the Hippocampus). But it may depend on other mechanisms that control and modulate the release of neurotransmitters. Examples of independent presynaptic LTP are those that originate in the parallel cerebellar fibers and the LTP of the corticothalamic terminals (Pickel & Segal, 2014, p. 72). This intensification in signal transmission between neurons can last from minutes to several months.

“Astroglia” intervenes in the regulation and absorption of glutamate released by the presynaptic neuron. Also, it releases a coagonist (D-serine) from “glutamate receptors” (NMDA), which allows regulating, remotely, the activation of these receptors, which induces LTP.

The extracellular matrix (EMC) is involved in the induction of neuronal plasticity, which is dependent on NMDA receptors. The cleavage of *agrin* does not only require the release of *neurotrypsin*, as we have seen but also the activation of the postsynaptic neuron (see Figure 10). The above constitutes another mechanism “simultaneity detector” that in this case triggers the “structural plasticity,” according to the principles elaborated by Hebb (Dityatev & Rusakov, 2011).

The EMC also controls the NMDA traffic through the *integrins*. On the other hand, it interconnects pre and postsynaptic protein complexes, stabilizing the interaction of both cells.

The postsynaptic neuron releases *neurotrophin* that stimulates neuronal growth and survival and promotes synaptogenesis. It can also produce LTP, as we have already mentioned.

Therefore, we can identify several forms of LTP:

- LTP Hebbian: simultaneous activation of pre and post-synaptic neurons (hippocampus, cortico-cortical, amygdala).
- LTP non-Hebbian: purely presynaptic (Hippocampus, thalamocortical, cortico-striatal).
- Anti-Hebbian LTP: requires that the postsynaptic neuron does not activate (interneurons).

The previous classification shows that the LTP mechanism is involved in all the circuits defined in the theory of the psychic apparatus taken as reference, as controllers of the different aspects of reality that has to deal with, a human.

Fig. 11. Bicyclic PAU of structural memory

The synapse not only constitutes an adequate connection between neurons so that a certain stimulus can be transmitted to the effector organ, but it is part of the memory. The first to suggest this was Sigmund Freud (1895) when he expounded his theory of “contact-barriers” [synapses]:

“There are two kinds of neurons. In the first place, those that let the excitement pass as if they had no contact-barrier, and therefore after each excitatory course remain in the same state as before, and, secondly, those whose contact-barriers oppose a difficulty to the passage of excitement. These, after each excitement, may remain in a state other than before, and thus result in a possibility of constituting the memory.” (Volume I AE, 1992, p.343).

The second that proposed a similar mnemonic mechanism was Donald Hebb in 1949 when in his book “*The organization of behavior*”, introduces the idea of a very particular synapse, which is what has come to our days as “Hebbian synapses.” This mechanism assumes that the persistence or repetition of a reverberant activity tends to induce lasting cellular changes that point to cellular stability. (Hebb, 2002, p.62) This rule supports the basic algorithm of learning through artificial neural networks while explaining how conditioned reflexes work and suggesting a possible mechanism of memory.

From the electrical point of view, Figure 11 shows that the synapse has been represented by a memristor, one of the components proposed for the construction of non-volatile memories used in computing. Thus, we have formed an RM (resistor-memristor) circuit. Memristors are 'resistors with memory,' hence their name (See Appendix). This behavior is based on the change between two resistive states (high and low) according to the direction of the electric charge (q). If the voltage (v) is disconnected, this special resistance 'remembers' until the next time it is connected, the resistance that was generated on the previous occasion. Chua says that all non-volatile memory based on a 'resistor switching' is a memristor. This fundamental element is a dynamic system that has a linear behavior (where there is a proportional relationship between cause and effect) and a non-linear behavior (where the previous proportionality disappears). But also, a memristor can be discreet or continuous. In this way, we can approach it without problems from the TL, since it behaves like a PAU.

All memristors exhibit a distinctive 'fingerprint' characterized by a “hysteresis loop” confined to the first and third quadrants of the v - i plane, as shown in the diagram on the right of Figure 11. Its outline changes with the amplitude and frequency of any periodic 'sinusoidal wave,' a source of input voltage (v) or current source (i). This hysteresis loop that has the shape of the infinity symbol (∞), contracts and tends to a straight line as the frequency increases. ($w_1 < w_2$ of the scheme). Moreover, if a critical frequency is reached, the memristor behaves like a common resistance (Adamatzky & Chua, 2014, p.21) (Figure 12).

Fig. 12.Yogesh N. Joglekar, "Current-Voltage Characteristics of a Memristor"

<http://demonstrations.wolfram.com/CurrentVoltageCharacteristicsOfAMemristor/>
Wolfram Demonstrations Project

In Figure 12 we see a simulation of the hysteresis loop of a memristor using software, whose analytical results arise from an original investigation carried out by Joglekar & Wolf in 2009. In the scheme, different recordings have been superimposed, varying the period of an alternating current. It is illustrative how the shape of the loop changes as we change the frequency. That is, the response of the memristor becoming more linear, approaching the behavior of a common resistance, as the frequency decreases (or the period increases).

Everything we have said It allows to demonstrate the generation of cyclic behavior, whose frequency can be 'remembered.' In the theory about the psychic apparatus that we have proposed, a similar mechanism is invoked to record, by 'storage' of frequencies, how the sequence was since a stimulus entered (from the real biological, psychic or sociocultural system), what Neurological structures were put into operation to elaborate a response (depending on whether we have already done this task before), and finally, on what system we should project it, leaving a record if necessary, of having learned a new routine. All this is perfectly represented in the dynamics of the "Bicyclic PAU" of Figure 11. This is a new type of PAU that allows considering its two levels (superficial and deep, linear and non-linear, discrete and continuous), but in alternating form, mimicking the hysteresis loop of a memristor.

5.0 CONCLUSION

We have been able to verify throughout this work that it is possible to emulate, through TL, the fundamental neural processes, using a model that integrates the three basic passive electrical elements (that dissipate or store energy): a capacitor, a resistor, and an inductor.

Through the different circuits generated by the combination of the above elements, a neuron could: capture a certain frequency, that is, "perceive" a real system. Trigger an "action potential" as a response and synchronize that response with the perceived real system.

If you add to this elementary circuit, as the fourth electrical component a memristor, the neuron could "store" in its synapse, to remember later, the "frequency" (or the real system) that generated the learning and what was capitalized as knowledge, in addition to "knowing" about over what "real system" should project its response.

Fig. 13. Structural memory

References: S: subject - O: perceived object - V: the transformation that relates S and O - ∇ : reference system. 80 Hz: bio-external system - 40 Hz: psycho-internal system - 20 Hz: socio-cultural system.

Figure 13 is intended to represent the theoretical disposition that would have the "structural memory," which is where it is supposed to reside the "psychic structure" or "history" of a subject. The use of a memristor in the electric model that we have proposed would allow to "capture" and "store" in non-volatile form, the relations raised by a "real fact" (relations of an S and O through a V transformation) perceived to have "sense" for the subject. The "density of transformations" (in the form of a beam of light) affecting the perceived objects is inversely proportional to the frequency that governs the respective real system, maintaining as background the same reference system (∇) that is not other than the "subjectivity" that determines the reality in which we are immersed.

REFERENCES

- Adamatzky, A.; Chua, L. (2014). *Memristor Networks*. Switzerland, Springer International Publishing.
- Berstein, J. (1868). *Ueber den zeitlichen Verlauf der negativen Schwankung des Nervenstroms*. Archiv für die gesamte Physiologie des Menschen und der Tiere, 1, ss. 173–207
- Dityatev, A.; Rusakov, D. A. (2011). *Molecular signals of plasticity at the tetrapartite synapse*. Curr Opin Neurobiol. April; 21(2), pp. 353-359.
- Du Bois-Reymond, E. (1848-1849). *Untersuchungen über thierische Elektrizität* G.E. Reimer. Berlin
- Freud, S. (1992). *Proyecto de psicología (1895) - Sigmund Freud. Obras completas, Tomo I*, pp. 323-436 - Buenos Aires, Amorrortu Editores. (AE)
- Galvani, L. (1797). *Memoire sulla elettricità animale*. Bologna: Sassi "Memoria quinta." pp. 66-68.
- González Montoya, S.; Arias Varón, D. (2014). *El Memristor, Aplicaciones circuitales con amplificadores operacionales*. Escuela de Tecnología Eléctrica, Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira, Colombia.
- Hebb, D. O. (2002 - 1949). *The Organization of Behavior. A Neuropsychological Theory* - New Jersey, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- Helmholtz, H. von. (1854). *Über die geschwindigkeit einiger vorgänge in muskeln und nerve*. Bericht über die zur bekanntmachung geeigneten verhandlungen der königlichen. Preuss Akad Wiss., Berlin. pp. 328-332
- Hodgkin, A.; Huxley, A. (1952). *A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve*. J. Physiol. (Lond) 117, pp. 500-544
- Joglekar, Y. N.; Wolf, S. J. (2009). *The elusive memristor: properties of basic electrical circuits*. Eur. J. Phys. 30, 661.
- Kandel, E. R. et al. (2013). *Principles of neural science*. New York, Mc Graw Hill.
- Lara Canto, C. E.; Fernández García, F. A. (2010). *Memristores: Teoría, Desarrollo y Aplicaciones del "Eslabón Perdido" en la Electrónica*. Universidad Tecnológica Metropolitana, Santiago de Chile.
- Llinás, R. (1988). *The intrinsic Electrophysiological properties of mammalian neurons. Insights into central nervous system function*. Science, 242, pp. 1654-1664.
- Matteucci, C. (1844). *Traité des Phénomènes Electro-physiologiques des Animaux suivi d'Etudes Anatomiques sur le Système Nerveux et sur l'Organe Electrique de la Torpille*. Fortin et Masson, Paris
- Mayergoyz, I. (2003). *Mathematical Models of Hysteresis and their Applications*. New York, Elsevier Science Inc.

- Nernst, W. (1907). *Experimental and Theoretical Applications of Thermodynamics to Chemistry*. New York, Charles Scribner's Sons.
- Pickel, V.; Segal, M. (2014). *The Synapse: Structure and Function*. Oxford, Elsevier.
- Radwan, A. G.; Fouda, M. E. (2015). *On the Mathematical Modeling of Memristor, Memcapacitor, and Meminductor*. Switzerland, Springer.
- Randall, D.; Burggren, W.; French, K. (1997). *Eckert Animal Physiology. Mechanisms and Adaptations*. Fourth Edition. New York, W. H. Freeman and Company.
- Salatino, D. R. (2009). *Semiótica de los sistemas reales – Tesis Doctoral en Letras – Facultad de Filosofía y Letras – Universidad Nacional de Cuyo - Mendoza, Argentina*.
- Salatino, D. R. (2012). *Aspectos psico-bio-socioculturales del lenguaje natural humano. Introducción a la teoría psíquica del lenguaje - Mendoza, Argentina - Desktop Publishing, Amazon, ISBN: 978-987-33-2379-9*.
- Salatino, D. R. (2013). *Psiquis – Estructura y función – Mendoza, Argentina – Autoedición. ISBN: 978-987-33-3808-3*.
- Salatino, D. R. (2017). *Tratado de Lógica Transcursiva. Origen evolutivo del sentido en la realidad subjetiva. Mendoza, Argentina, Primera Autoedición – ISBN: 978-987-42-5099-5*.
- Siskind, C. S. (1972). *Circuitos Eléctricos*. Buenos Aires, Editorial Hispano Americana, S. A.
- Vourkas, I.; Sirakoulis, G. Ch. (2016). *Memristor-Based Nanoelectronic Computing Circuits and Architectures*. Switzerland, Springer.

APPENDIX

MEMRISTOR

In the year of 1971 a professor of electrical engineering at the University of California, Berkeley L. Chua, predicted the existence of a fourth fundamental device, called the *memristor* verifying that it was not possible to create a duplicate of this element with the combination of the other three devices, by, therefore, according to this statement the *memristor* is a fundamental device.

To better understand the theoretical studies of Leon Chua, it must be said that he was based on an ideography that dates back to the thought of Aristotle and his disciples (Figure 1A).

Fig. 1A. PAU of the Fundamental components of the matter

Aristotle assumes that all things have as distinctive aspects a matter and a form, that is, they make up a system or set of elements (matter), provided with structure (form). Thus, it relates the four elements with which matter was explained in the ancient Greek world: Earth, Water, Fire, Air, which link with four elements originated by their combinations: Heat, Cold, Moisture, Dryness.

Figure 2A shows the existence of the three fundamental elements, and it was there that Professor L. Chua justified the existence of a fourth passive element for electronics, elaborating the theory of what is known as *memristor*.

Fig. 2A. Integration of memristive systems

It is not trivial to define the generic mathematical form that describes the behavior of the *memristor*, for it is taken as an initial hypothesis the fact that the Memristor is a resistance and that implicitly must be measured in Ohms (Ω).

The fundamental relationship of electric charge and magnetic flux are variables that define the *memristor* as the fourth element of circuit theory and can be expressed by two integrals:

$$d\varphi(t) = v(t)dt \rightarrow \varphi(t) = \int v(t)dt$$

$$dq(t) = i(t)dt \rightarrow q(t) = \int i(t)dt$$

It can be said that a memristor can be controlled by electric charge, if the relation between the magnetic flux and the electric charge is expressed as a function of the electric charge q ; and it can be said that a memristor can be controlled by magnetic flux, if the relation between the magnetic flux and the electric charge is expressed as a function of the flux φ .

$$\frac{v(t)}{i(t)} = \frac{df(q)}{dq} = M(q)$$

(q) , is called the memristance which has the unit of resistance, and defines a linear relationship between current and voltage, as long as the electric charge did not change. Then M is a constant; therefore, a memristor behaves like a resistor.

For a *memristor* controlled by magnetic flux,

$$q = f(\varphi)$$

(φ) , is called the *memductance* which has the unit of conductance.

The memristance is a property of the memristor, when the electric charge flows in one direction through a circuit, the resistance of the memristor increases. The resistance of the memristor decreases when the electric charge flows in the opposite direction in the circuit. If the applied voltage disconnects, then the charge flow ceases, so, the memristor "remembers" the last resistance that passed through the memristor. When the charge flow starts again, the resistance of the circuit will be what it was when it was active (Figure 3A).

Fig. 3A. Memristance

The memristor belongs to the dynamic systems, given its ability to "remember" with a linear and non-linear behavior. It must be remembered that the state of a static system depends only on the present conditions and not on the past. In contrast, the state of a dynamic system depends on what happened in the past, usually because there is some type of energy storage in the system. Dynamic systems are also known as "memory systems". Therefore, the memristor is a passive and dynamic system that has memory but is not an energy storage device. The properties of the memristor are perceptible, only, on a small scale (nanoscale).

It consists of a pure platinum substrate, to which titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is deposited in its upper part, then another deposit of titanium dioxide followed by another platinum substrate. The difference between the two oxides lies in the fact that one is missing oxygen atoms (TiO_{2-x}), these missing atoms act as charge carriers. (This announcement was made by Williams in 2008) (Figure 4A).

Fig. 4A. Composition of memristor

This configuration is as good a conductor as metals. When oxygen atoms are removed from titanium dioxide, the "holes" they leave (absences of negative charges) behave as positive charges, similar to electrons in a classical PN junction. A positive tension pushes the positive charges to the right inside the other TiO_2 , as illustrated in the anterior figure, in this way the thickness of TiO_{2-x} "increases" at the same time as the thickness of TiO_2 "decreases." After a while, the separation between the dioxides stops being the one marked by the blue line to become the one marked by the red line. By placing a negative voltage, we can invert the process and increase the thickness of TiO_2 .